

EARLY EDUCATION PROGRESS ASSESSMENT

By Edwin Amuga

The years between Birth and first grade are crucial in creating a foundation for later school successes in many children. The skills the students develop at the kindergarten or one grade level must be built upon and reinforced in later grades. For students to sustain the grades they achieved in kindergarten or lower grades, they must continue to receive high-quality teaching in subsequent grades.

There has been a growing effort to expand quality pre-kindergarten opportunities for young children to close the gaps in early achievement. This is though threatened by lack of access to a high-quality continuum of learning that would contribute to making the gap differences positive. These gaps and disparities in learning exist even as children enter pre-kindergarten and further persist and grower larger throughout early elementary school. Recent studies have pointed out that fewer than 50% of third graders achieve mastery in reading or math. The picture portends even the worst for vulnerable youth.

Despite the enormous efforts employed by the many early childhood community networks and school districts on many fronts to ensure the improvement of the quality of education in pre-kindergarten through Kindergarten right from birth, a number of challenges still remain including the different beliefs on what and how children should learn across the progression, misaligned curriculum programs or ineffective implementation of quality programs, conflicting professional development priorities and goal, teacher observation inconsistent use, lack of family engagement and awareness of the available support services for families and

children and lack of or disconnected assessment methods such as screening and progress monitoring.

There is a need for building a support system for early learning to help prepare all children to achieve mastery in reading and math in first grade and beyond and this will mean a concerted effort of implementers, teachers and system leaders to embrace policies and practices that support a consistent, coherent approach to early education with continuous and enhanced learning opportunities for young children. Studies have identified a number of strategies that are effective in ensuring the alignment of efforts from birth through pre-k and kindergarten. These include the implementation of high quality curricula, providing a positive support system for families and children, effective use of teacher observation system, shared curriculum and content-specific professional development between birth and K-3 and, most importantly, the use of meaningful assessment methods that include early and accurate identification (Tayler, Cloney, Adams, Ishimine, Thorpe & Nguyen, 2016).

There are two types of methods that can be used when looking across the spectrum of measures designed to examine what young children know and can do. These are direct assessment and observation-based assessment. Direct assessment is a formal typical and standardized measurement in which all children are presented with the same parallel questions or identification of tasks. The timing, sample terms and prompts occur in parallel or the same fashion. Observation-based assessments, on the other hand, are informal, authentic assessment approaches in which teachers observe children daily as they engage in everyday program activities and within natural settings. Teachers use anecdotal notes and student work samples to document the performance and progress of learning of children over time. A well-structured assessment is appropriate to the development and experiences of young children, aligned to the

standards and student learning goals and conducted in a language children are comfortable with and include appropriate accommodations. It is more appropriate to use observation as a mechanism to use gathering assessment information. Observation allows children to demonstrate a skill or behavior in multiple settings and across time. With the increase of age, using direct assessment should be used more frequently but with balance with informal methods. For instance, assessment practices in pre-kindergarten should generally be around 100% observation. Assessment practices for kindergarten should be around 75% observation and 25% direct. For K-2, there should be 50% use of observation and 50% use of direct assessment. In K-3 and first grade, there should be 25% observation and 75% direct assessments. With further advancement of age and grades, there should be further increased in the use of direct assessment towards 100% (Tayler, Cloney, Adams, Ishimine, Thorpe & Nguyen, 2016).

A comprehensive assessment plan developed should serve three main purposes. These include screening children at the beginning of the year to identify delayed development risks and academic failures and the need for additional support or intervention to achieve-age level standards by end year. The second purpose is diagnosing specific needs of at-risk children that will be helpful in providing additional instruction or services that meet the most critical learning needs and the third purpose is to monitoring the progress of children during the year to determine whether they are making adequate progress and to identify those who may be trailing. Before assessments and after assessments are carried out, parents should be kept informed in advance about the purpose and focus of these assessments. When assessments are meant for screening, families should be informed about the results especially when they indicate the need for further diagnostic assessment.

Assessment chart

References

Taylor, C., Cloney, D., Adams, R., Ishimine, K., Thorpe, K., & Nguyen, T. K. C. (2016).

Assessing the effectiveness of Australian early childhood education and care experiences: study protocol. *BMC public health*, *16*(1), 352.